

THE WORK OF KHALED HOSSEINI AND HIS PLACE IN WORLD LITERATURE

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Annotation

Humor is an example of a phenomenon whose study requires an interdisciplinary approach. Due to its versatility, humor (as well as the related concepts of “laughter”, “laughter culture” and “sense of humor”) are studied from the standpoint of many sciences.

The greatest contribution to understanding the development of a sense of humor has been introduced by the discipline "age psychology". A review of the results obtained within the framework of this discipline is necessary for researchers of all scientific fields.

Keywords

N.N. Nosov, humor, children's game, fairy tales, laughter, children's perception of the world.

When studying almost any literary work, it is necessary to know the biography of the author, because without knowing how the writer lived, we cannot fully understand and feel his work. So, Khaled Hosseini was born in 1965 in Kabul (the capital of Afghanistan). He grew up in a rich, large family of an Afghan diplomat (As far as I know, large families live in Afghanistan). His mother was a teacher at a girls' school in Kabul. In 1976, Khaled's family moved to Paris, where his father received a post at the Afghan embassy. They were supposed to return home in 1980, but it was at that time that a big coup took place in the country, and Soviet

troops entered there. This coup greatly affected all Afghan families, many civilians left their homeland, including Khaled's family. His family received political asylum in the United States. There they settled in California. Khaled studied medicine at Santa Clara University and the University of California. For some time he worked in his specialty, and then he began to write novels telling the Western world about Eastern civilization and the history of Afghanistan.

How did the Afghan people survive the tsarist time? Why was the democratic system poorly perceived? Because the Afghan people live in Islamic culture. And even today there are Islamic radicals who are supporters of Islam and who oppose the democratic regime.

H. Hosseini became known to the general public after the release of the book "The Kite Runner ". Also, in addition to writing, Khaled acts as an employee of the UN refugee agency. H. Hosseini is actively helping the Afghans. He is one of the founders of a fund to help Afghan children affected by mines.

Penetrating, penetrating to the very core, about friendship and fidelity, about betrayal and redemption, gentle, ironic and in a good way sentimental Khaled Hosseini's novel resembles a painting that can be looked at endlessly.

The story takes place in pre-war Kabul in the 1970s. In this magical city, shimmering with all shades of gold and azure, two boys live Amir and Hassan. One belongs to the local aristocracy, the other to a despised minority. For one, the father was handsome and important, for the other, lame and pathetic. Master and servant, prince and beggar, handsome man and cripple. But there were no closer friends in the world than these two boys. Soon, the Kabul idyll will be replaced by a formidable storm, and the boys, like two kites, will be picked up and carried away in different directions. Everyone has their own fate, their own tragedy, but they, as in childhood, are connected by strong ties.

My first encounter with Hosseini was very exciting. After reading his novel The Kite Runner, I felt as if I was in Afghanistan for a minute. The novel is easy to

read. There are no complex literary terms, and it suits those readers who have an average level of Russian. Although I lived in a neighboring state, I did not know that there was such a deeply analyzing, authoritative writer in Afghanistan. Therefore, I am very grateful to my supervisor Olga Borisovna for offering me to read and write a term paper on this novel. The American writer of Afghan origin H. Hosseini perfectly emphasized that between Afghans, Sunnis and Shiites (these religious streams) there is not only a common Eastern culture and friendship, but there are also betrayals and, of course, redemption.

This novel is set in Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, and the United States of America. It should be noted that the characters are Muslims. The story is told from the perspective of Amir, a boy from the city of Kabul. He comes from a wealthy family and is related to a vizier (minister) who is Pashtun. Today, most of the nationalities of Afghanistan are Pashtuns. Amir lived in a traditional Oriental-style orphanage with his father, Baba, a wealthy man. He is an architect and builder by profession. His father loved to draw blueprints, and he liked to build houses according to his blueprints. Amir's mother died at the birth of her son. From childhood, it seemed to Amir that his father did not love him very much, because he could not forgive him for his involuntary guilt in the death of his wife. From an early age, Amir's companion in the games was Hassan, the son of his father's servant. Hassan's family were Hazaras. The Hazaras are one of the national minorities in Afghanistan, who were often treated as second-class people. I want to say that in many countries there is a situation where urban residents are not always polite to other peoples. Sometimes, there is even strong aggression and cruel treatment of these peoples, who are considered in this country to be the lowest stratum of society.

However, Amir's father treated Hasan very warmly, gave him expensive gifts, did not scold, but always praised him. But dad was not so kind to Amir, and Amir was often jealous of his friend for his own father.

Each Afghan region, each district has its own traditional games, one of which is called "Kite". Amir and Hassan used to play this game with street boys every year.

My dad told me about the kite. He told me that as a child he also played this game. I never once asked my father about the games of his childhood, but fate itself sent this book to me, and I learned about the existence of such a game.

In the novel, the kite symbolizes the fate of the two boys.

In 1975, as usual, there was a massive kite-flying competition in Kabul. As I said, kite flying is one of the most beloved annual events among the people. You can guess that the more kites, the more interesting the competition will be. The winner was the one whose kite remained in the air the longest, cutting off the lines of the others, and who picked up the last one that fell. Imagine that you are also a witness of this competition, around the field and the sky is filled with many kites of different colors. Everyone gathered around you from the old to the young. Fans scream, competitors overtake each other, trying to keep the kite in the air as long as possible.

Embraced by the thought of surprising his father, Amir decided that winning the competition would help him regain his favor. During the competition, Amir and Hasan won the first victory, and their kite remained in the air the longest, but it was necessary to find the kite that fell last. Hasan was, although illiterate, but a talented boy to predict the location of a fallen kite, and he ran to catch it. Seeing that Hassan for some reason did not return for a long time, the excited Amir ran to look for him and saw how his old enemy, Asef, was mocking Hasan.

Of course, Asef was unhappy with the fact that the younger ones were winning, and therefore decided to teach them a lesson.

Asef was distinguished by nationalist views and a penchant for sadism. He not only mocked Hassan in words, but also beat him. From people prone to sadism, you can only expect a deplorable result, and no matter what age, young or old.

I will cover this in detail in the next chapter.

Amir was a literate boy, he loved to read shahnam, literature and folk tales. In the evenings, the boys played cards and prepared a kite for the upcoming competitions. Amira liked to read stories and retell them to others, and Hasan, frankly, could not read, as he was illiterate. This situation shows their fate and the difference in living standards. In the future, Amir became a teacher, and Hasan grew up the way he was in his childhood. However, Baba loved Hassan more. This always angered Amir and he decided to slip the watch and birthday present into Hasan's pocket to show what the underclass really are and cannot be trusted. I believe that a person from the lower stratum of society should never be an authority over those above. If this process continues like this, in the future Hassan will become a big person (a businessman or a vizier of one city), then Amir cannot have such an authoritative degree. That's why he invented betrayal.

That night there was a scandal between Baba and the servant's family. Of course, they found everything stolen in Hassan's pocket. He was suspected of theft and kicked out. Despite Baba's pleas to stay, the servants leave the house and go to another city. The former life ended forever, and for Amir a quiet life began.

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